

PRODUCTION OF MEAT PRODUCTS

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***Annotation.** The purpose of this article is to broadly cover the meat production process and its technological foundations, and to focus on quality and safety issues. One of the main objectives of this article is to give an idea of how developed this industry is today and how the quality of products is ensured.*

***Key words:** Meat industry, meat processing, canned meat, sausage products, smoked meat, semi-finished products, technological process, quality control, food safety.*

The production of meat products is one of the important food industries that serves to provide people with high quality protein and important nutrients. Meat products include fresh meat, canned meat, sausages, smoked products and semi-finished products.

Today, this industry is developing on the basis of high technology, in order to ensure the quality and safety of products, modern equipment and production technologies are used. The process of meat processing is carried out taking into account biological, chemical and physical properties.

It is also important to produce products in accordance with the requirements and tastes of consumers. This article provides detailed information about the process of meat products production, its main stages, technological processes and quality control. The process of production of meat products. The production of meat products consists of several important stages, each of which is carried out on the basis of special technological processes.

1. Preparation of raw materials

The process of production of meat products begins, first of all, with quality raw materials.

Meat coming from livestock farms or slaughterhouses is analyzed in special laboratories to check its quality and safety.

2. Meat processing

Meat processing is based on various technologies: Cutting and separating - fat, bones and other unnecessary parts are separated from the meat. Storage at the appropriate temperature - since meat is a perishable product, it is important to refrigerate or freeze it. Marinating and seasoning - special methods are used to flavor the product and preserve it for a longer period of time.

3. meat product safety and environmental concerns

Reducing carbon footprint: Large companies (e.g., Tyson Foods, JBS, and Cargill) are implementing clean energy use to reduce carbon emissions. Antibiotic-free meat: Consumers are increasing demand for antibiotic-free meat products for health reasons, forcing producers to comply with new standards.

4. New meat products and trends Fermentation technology: Fermentation-based meat

products have entered the market as a new method of protein production. Halal and Kosher certified products: There is a growing demand in the international market for meat products specifically designed for Muslim and Jewish consumers.

Recent innovations in meat production have developed along the following lines:

1. Plant-based and artificial meat products. Lab-grown meat: expanding the activities of large artificial meat companies in the US and Europe. For example, companies such as UPSIDE Foods and Eat Just produce artificial meat for the commercial market. Plant-based alternatives: brands such as Beyond Meat and Impossible Foods continue to refine their plant-based products as an alternative to conventional meat.

2. New technologies in the meat industry: Blockchain and IoT (Internet of Things): The use of blockchain technologies to accurately track the origin of meat products is expanding. For example, Japan has implemented a system to track the movement of meat using digital monitoring systems.

Automated processing systems: With the help of robotics, meat processing and packaging processes are more efficient and hygienic.

3. meat product safety and environmental concerns: Reducing carbon footprint: Large companies (e.g. Tyson Foods, JBS and Cargill) are introducing clean energy use to reduce carbon emissions. Antibiotic-free meat: Consumers are increasing demand for antibiotic-free meat products for health reasons, forcing producers to comply with new standards.

4. New meat products and trends: Fermentation technology: Fermentation-based meat products have entered the market as a new method of protein production.

Halal and Kosher certified products: There is a growing demand in the international market for meat products specifically designed for Muslim and Jewish consumers. The meat production sector is developing intensively, and major changes are taking place in the environment, health and technology. More innovations in this area are expected in the coming years. The production of meat products is a complex and multi-stage process that requires special technologies and quality control. In modern industry, great attention is paid to the production of environmentally friendly and high-quality products. Also one of the important directions is the production of new types of products in accordance with the tastes of consumers. Safety and quality of meat products depend not only on producers, but also on consumers. Proper storage and consumption allow you to get the maximum benefit from quality meat products.

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